

Blending of a novel all sky imager model with persistence and a satellite based model for high-resolution irradiance nowcasting

Nils Straub^{*}, Wiebke Herzberg, Anna Dittmann, Elke Lorenz

Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE, Freiburg, Germany

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ABSTRACT

High shares of variable energy sources such as photovoltaics (PV) make balancing network load and generation increasingly challenging. Electricity grids with high PV-penetration benefit from the consideration of intra-minute and intra-hour variabilities via nowcasts (shortest-term forecasts).

In this study we present a novel all-sky imager (ASI) nowcasting system which is benchmarked against an established ASI method, a satellite nowcasting system and persistence. Nowcasts of our novel ASI method, satellite method and persistence are subsequently combined to a hybrid model with improved accuracy.

ASI systems exploit sky images from fisheye cameras to analyze sky conditions, predict upcoming cloud situations and derive irradiance nowcasts from these. Our ASI method uses a novel machine-learning (ML) based approach that makes direct use of pixel values and other image features. Measurements from a spatially distributed irradiance measuring network of eight stations within a radius of 10km around the camera position are used to train our ASI and our hybrid model and validate our nowcasting results. In the evaluation we put a special focus on irradiance variability conditions. The high share of stable cloud situations within our dataset (~68 %) results in a relatively good performance of persistence nowcasts. In higher variability situations persistence is quickly outperformed by all other nowcasting methods.

Our ASI method clearly outperforms the reference ASI method at all lead times (LTs). It moreover exhibits a significantly lower root mean square error (RMSE) than the satellite-based method up to $LT \leq 11 \text{ min}$ ahead and a lower mean absolute error (MAE) throughout the entire interval. The hybrid model brings about an RMSE improvement score of 5–13% over the respective optimal individual method.

1. Introduction

Due to the fast extension of installed solar energy capacity worldwide, the generation characteristics within our electricity grids are in the process of undergoing a fundamental transformation. Rather than in relatively few major power plants driven with conventional resources, electricity is generated more and more in numerous distributed plants of variable size.

With the integration of large shares of distributed variable energy sources, [6] name a share of beyond 15 % of annual energy production, a need for significant changes in the operation of electrical grids arises. Unaltered operation however can lead to severe instabilities [49,11,34,1].

Synoptic and local weather patterns make solar irradiance a highly variable resource. Its forecasts hence make an important contribution to

the integration of large shares of PV into the electricity grid [42]. Thereby different methods on different spatial and temporal scales are deployed to cover all relevant lead times (LTs). On a local scale, irradiance levels can fluctuate with high amplitude on very short time scales (seconds to minutes), also referred to as irradiance ramps. These ramps are caused by passing clouds and result in sudden and heavy fluctuations in the power production of large PV-powerplants or distributed PV within quarters. This sets new challenges for all stakeholders including plant and grid operators.

Forecasts of solar irradiance based on numerical weather predictions (NWP) and the images of meteorological satellites have become well established approaches to forecast solar irradiance days or hours ahead respectively, covering a wide field of applications [42,23]. However, due to their temporal and spatial resolution neither of them can resolve small-scale cloud structures and movements with higher resolution,

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: nils.straub@ise.fraunhofer.de (N. Straub), wiebke.herzberg@ise.fraunhofer.de (W. Herzberg), anna.dittmann@ise.fraunhofer.de (A. Dittmann), elke.lorenz@ise.fraunhofer.de (E. Lorenz).

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which makes them unsuitable for predicting irradiance ramps.

To do so, more highly resolved forecasts for the immediate future, also referred to as nowcasts, are required. To generate nowcasts on-site observations from ground-based fisheye cameras facing the sky, so called all sky imagers (ASIs) and local irradiance measurements are used. Based on these, fine-grained control applications can be performed to handle short-term fluctuations of PV-power in a way beneficial for the grid and other stakeholders involved.

The control of heat pumps and cooling systems [9], as well as management of large battery storages, offgrid PV-Diesel systems and solar thermal power plants and the short-term electricity market [42] are just a few examples of applications that can benefit from accurate nowcasting. With ever increasing shares of PV, nowcasts might eventually also play an important role on a larger scale for managing the operation of peak load power plants efficiently.

In this study we benchmark a novel all sky imager (ASI) nowcasting method against an established ASI model [8], satellite-based (SAT) nowcasts and a persistence model. We evaluate our models' performances under different irradiance variability conditions, to get a full picture of their benefits and drawbacks.

Our first nowcasting approach is a persistence model, assuming persistence of clear-sky index at the respective position. The clear-sky index k_{clear}^* is defined as the ratio between current global horizontal irradiance (GHI) and GHI under clear-sky conditions [42]. Secondly, we use a satellite-based approach [22] based on the well-established Heliosat method [16]. Using images of Meteosat Second Generation (MSG) forecasts with a temporal resolution of 15 min up to a few hours ahead can be computed. Within this study we only use the first LT step (15 min ahead), which is linearly interpolated to create nowcasts that match the 1-minute resolution of the ASI.

With its capability to predict short-term irradiance variability a novel ASI model is the centrepiece of our blending experiments. Here we use an adapted version of the model we initially reported of in [44]. ASIs capture images of the sky in regular intervals to track clouds and their motion. Future cloud situations are predicted by extrapolating these movements into the future. Nowcasts are computed by modelling radiative effects of clouds with a machine learning (ML) approach and applying the information to predicted cloud situations.

To create areal forecasts clouds must be geolocated either using the cloud base height (CBH) from ceilometer measurements or multiple ASIs with overlapping fields of view to perform stereo photography. Subsequently, cloud shadows are projected onto their real-world positions on the ground exploiting cloud and sun position. Thereby spatial coverage and forecasting horizon can be extended by using multiple or even networks of ASIs [41,38]. Nevertheless many ASI methods reported of only generate point nowcasts (usually for the camera position) not providing any spatial resolution [25,33,17]. With the growing share of solar energy in electricity grids worldwide the significance of and the research on these high-resolution nowcasting systems have drastically increased throughout the past decade.

Although commercial sky imager cameras exist [5,35] frequently just regular off-the-shelf fisheye cameras are deployed [30,39,7,33,8]. Besides hardware, the key for good ASI nowcasting lies in the models and algorithms to evaluate images and supplementary GHI measurements.

A common approach for irradiance retrieval for ASI nowcasting is to evaluate the short-term history of irradiance measurements retrieving binary clear-sky indices for either shaded or sun exposed positions using statistical methods [39,8]. Cloud decision algorithms, based on the red-blue ratio of image pixels [39,9] or on ML methods like neuronal networks [13,47], are applied to sky images to discriminate between shaded or sun exposed sites. A probabilistic approach for irradiance modelling from sky images is proposed in [29] by correlating cloud transmittance with cloud base height, exploiting both historical and recent cloud height and transmittance measurements.

Transmittance of radiative power through clouds can be derived for each image pixel separately by using an infrared camera system [25] by applying the method described in [51]. Downsides of these systems are among others lower resolution and higher costs compared to optical cameras. In more recent publications convolutional neuronal networks are deployed to process series of ASI images within an end-to-end process to derive nowcasts of solar irradiance [15,14].

Our novel ASI method uses an ML algorithm trained on spatially distributed measurements of GHI from a network of measuring stations to retrieve GHI levels from pixel values and other image features. Thereby each image pixel is assigned a specific, distinct GHI value. This allows more flexible modelling of complex cloud situations with distinct transmittances compared to the usage of binary clear-sky indices. The combination of ML and spatially distributed irradiance measurements to yield areal maps of GHI represents a new approach in the field of ASI nowcasting. Using training data from a measuring network multiplies the amount of training data captured within a certain time period and provides measurements with a spatial dimension to enhance areal nowcasting. In [44] we showed that this new method outperforms the established ASI method from [8] on all lead times (LTs) up to 15 min ahead. As a second novelty, nowcasts from our novel ASI method are blended with SAT and persistence nowcasts to a hybrid model for optimized nowcasting throughout the entire short-term interval.

Combination of different forecasting models is a common approach that reduces forecasting errors compared to the respective individual methods. In [21] NWP, SAT and persistence PV-power forecasts are combined using a LT-dependent linear regression approach for forecasting PV power. Blending approaches for SAT, NWP and persistence forecasts by the means of different ML-methods such as Extreme Gradient Boosting and Support Vector Machines have been studied in [48,18,19].

Although the combination of different models is a common approach in the field of irradiance forecasting, it has been hardly investigated within the short-term interval and (to the author's best knowledge) the benefit of combining persistence, ASI and SAT nowcasts has not been demonstrated yet. [30] combine ASI and persistence nowcasts by weighting them based on their respective root mean square error (RMSE) within recent historical nowcasts. A hybrid solar PV-power nowcasting model for the optimal combination of ASI and statistical nowcasts is presented in [17].

A first approach of combining ASI, SAT and persistence nowcasts is investigated in [26]. Thereby four different ASI, two satellite models and persistence are blended via different ML methods to create point nowcasts of GHI and direct normal irradiance DNI. Forecasting horizons of up to 90 min ahead were considered and general as well as LT-dependent blending has been investigated. This study was conducted in Southwestern Spain on a dataset of 43 preselected days.

Our study was performed in Freiburg, Germany, a region with different meteorological conditions and a higher occurrence of (convective) clouds. As mentioned, the core part of our blending approach is a novel ASI method, resulting in a significantly different hybrid model than the one described in [26]. In our evaluation we analyze the availability of nowcasts and put a special focus on nowcasting performance under different irradiance variability conditions.

This work is structured as follows: The used dataset and the measuring setup are outlined in section 2. Detailed descriptions of our nowcasting and our blending approach as well as evaluation method can be found in section 3. Nowcasting results and a variability analysis are presented in section 4. Section 5 summarizes our findings with overall conclusions.

2. Dataset

In the following our measuring setup and dataset used within this study are described. Our irradiance measurements run through a quality control (QC) procedure to ensure data quality. Forecast specifications

Fig. 1. Map of our irradiance measuring network. The marked circle has a radius of 10 km. The ASI is located in the center (marked red). Stations with a star are equipped with both MS80 and ML01 pyranometers, the remaining stations only with ML01 pyranometers. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Measurement station with EKO MS80, ML01 pyranometers and tilted reference cells. Within this work we only use EKO MS80 and ML01.

and training and test configurations of our ASI and hybrid models are likewise outlined in this section.

2.1. Measuring setup

We use GHI measurements from a network of eight measuring stations within Freiburg to evaluate our forecasting results and train our ASI- and hybrid models. These measuring stations are located within a radius of approximately 10km around the camera position (Fig. 1). An off-the-shelf surveillance camera (Vivotek FE9381) located in the center of the map is used as ASI, recording images every 10s. Four of the stations (tagged with a star) are equipped with a ventilated thermal pyranometer (EKO MS-80) which has a particularly low response time ($< 0.5s$) and a silicon pyranometer (EKO ML-01), as depicted in Fig. 2. The remaining stations are equipped with silicon pyranometers only. All sensors record instantaneous GHI with second resolution. Measurements from the thermal pyranometers are used, if available, because of their lower uncertainty [24,28]. Moreover, the station at the position of the sky imager is equipped with a sun tracker from EKO (STR-22G) measuring DNI with a pyrheliometer (MS-56) and diffuse horizontal irradiance DHI with a pyranometer shaded by a shadow ball (MS-802F). This sophisticated setup provides the highest measurement quality within the measuring network and is in the following referred to as sun tracking reference setup (STRS).

Additionally, our ASI-method uses ceilometer measurements of cloud base height (CBH) to generate areal forecasts of GHI. These come from a nearby ceilometer (distance to ASI $d_{ASI} \approx 1km$) operated by the German weather service Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD).

Table 1

Illustration of train test split of the ASI and hybrid model training. Splitting scheme continues after the depicted period throughout the entire dataset.

	Day of dataset:								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	...
ASI nowcasting	ASI Train	Nowcasting -Dataset	ASI Train	Nowcasting -Dataset	ASI Train	Nowcasting -Dataset	ASI Train	Nowcasting -Dataset	...
Hybrid nowcasting		Hybrid Training		Hybrid Test		Hybrid Training		Hybrid Test	...

2.2. Quality control

All irradiance measurements used within this work undergo an extensive quality control (QC) procedure to ensure data quality [43]. The scope of our QC method is to identify flawed measurements and, if possible, correct them or otherwise discard them.

Our QC method comprises the following steps:

1. Envelop-filter: Based on [12] a range of plausible irradiance measurements is defined. Measurements beyond this envelop are flagged as erroneous.
2. Harmonization for clear-sky days: Despite calibration we still find slight, but notable deviations between our measurement stations to which our ML methods are very sensitive. To harmonize our measurements these are compensated using correction factors. These factors were computed using quality-controlled measurements of the STMS from clear sky days.

Measurements of the EKO ML-01 pyranometers undergo the following additional steps:

3. Peak-filter: Measurements of the ML01 sparsely exhibit sharp peaks of 1–3 samples length (corresponding to 1–3 s) that do not result from transient shading. We assume electromagnetic fields at our testing sites to be the cause for these disturbances. As these erroneous values are not reliably filtered out in step 1, an additional filter based on the comparison to neighboring samples is applied.
4. Conversion: ML01 and MS80 have different measurement characteristics whereas the measurements of MS80 are generally of higher quality. An adopted version of the conversion method from [37] is applied to measurements of the ML01 to approximate the measurement characteristics of the MS80. Here we include steps to correct deviations due to differences in temperature dependence, angular and spectral response.

2.3. Training and test data

Our measuring campaign started in February 2018 and is running ever since. Within this study one entire year from (including) May 2021 to April 2022 was selected. Using one year of data aims at giving a balanced representation of the seasonal course of meteorological conditions on our testing site.

The dataset split for the ASI and the hybrid model is illustrated in Table 1. For training of the ASI irradiance retrieval method (compare section 3.1.1) all odd days of the year have been used. ASI, SAT and persistence nowcasts were computed in the remaining even days of the year (in the following nowcasting-dataset). Subsequently the nowcasting-dataset was split to create a training and test dataset for our hybrid method. As four entire are days missing in our nowcasting-dataset we use every second day *available* to split it into evenly sized train and test datasets.

Both, measurements and nowcasts used in this work are instantaneous values. Nowcasts are computed throughout the entire previously described periods for sun zenith angles of $\leq 80^\circ$ and with a temporal resolution of 1 min. In principle, our ASI method can provide finer

resolutions (down to 10 s) but as comparison to and combination with SAT nowcasts is the scope of this work minute resolution was chosen here. Due to the update frequency of satellite images nowcasts of all methods are computed with a base-time (starting time of each nowcast run) frequency of 15 min.

Nowcast LT is set to 15 min ahead. The maximum possible nowcasting horizon of our ASI method depends on the prevailing cloud conditions. It can be longer or less than the intended 15 min ahead. Truncated nowcast runs with a maximum LT of less than 15 min are considered in the evaluation. For these instances SAT and persistence nowcasts are filtered to the same maximum LT to ensure best possible comparability among our methods. An extensive analysis on the availability of ASI nowcasts is given in section 4.1.

3. Methodology

Nowcasting methods and our blending approach are presented in this section. Thereby the focus is on the description of our novel ASI approach. Descriptions of the other nowcasting methods are limited to a short summary. More detailed information on these can be found in the referenced publications. Moreover, our evaluation strategy including error metrics and variability analysis are outlined in this section.

3.1. ASI nowcasting

Our ASI nowcasting method uses camera images, local irradiance measurements at the position of the camera as well as CBH measurements to generate spatially and temporally highly resolved (1 min and $\approx 2 - 10$ m, depending on CBH) areal nowcasts of GHI. Our nowcasting chain is illustrated in Fig. 3. It builds on the ASI method described by [8] and includes the following steps:

- a) Recording of all sky image.
- b) Rectification to compensate fisheye distortion.
- c) Computation of clear-sky index images using ML-method.
- d) Identifying cloud movements by computing optical flow from two consecutive rectified ASI images.
- e) Prediction of future clear-sky index images by applying the computed optical flow to (c).
- f) Forecast of GHI maps by projecting clear-sky indices onto their real-world position and scaling them with computed clear-sky irradiation.

In this work we extend the original approach from point to areal nowcasting by geolocating clouds and projecting their shadows onto real-world positions. Instead of the statistical irradiance retrieval from recent GHI histograms, an adapted version of the ML method from [43,44] is used to assign distinct GHI levels to each image pixel (hereinafter irradiance algorithm). The remaining steps (a, b, d) and algorithms are equivalent to the original approach. The single steps are described in the following:

After recording, sky images are rectified (b) to compensate the fisheye distortion. Thereby the image is projected onto a regular grid. Using interpolation outer image areas are stretched, while the region around the optical center is compressed. For this step the projection

Fig. 3. Overview ASI nowcasting method. (a) recording of ASI image, (b) undistortion, (c) computation of clear-sky index image, (d) computation of optical flow, (e) forecasted clear-sky index image, (f) forecasted irradiance map. Note, that from step (e) to (f) the clear-sky image is mirrored along the y-axis as a result of the projection.

parameters of the camera are required, which were computed from images of a checkerboard. Assuming a two-dimensional layer of clouds within one horizontal plain, this method creates a map of current cloud

structures in the sky.

Subsequently (step (c)) a clear-sky index k^* is assigned to each image pixel by applying the irradiance algorithm to the undistorted ASI image

creating a highly resolved k^* -map (see following section 3.1.1). The clear-sky index is a key metric within our ASI method as it strongly mitigates (removes under ideal conditions) diurnal dependencies and solely reflects the impact of clouds on GHI. Using an appropriate clear-sky model it can be converted into GHI and vice versa. Here we compute clear-sky irradiance using the clear-sky model from [10] and the turbidity model from [3].

Future k^* -maps are generated by computing the optical flow (step (d)) (DeepFlow algorithm, from [46]) two subsequent undistorted sky images and scaling and applying this flow to the k^* -map (e). OpenCV [4] was used for the implementation of both the fisheye correction in (b) and the DeepFlow algorithm.

In the final step (f) the clear-sky indices in our forecasted maps are converted into GHI and projected to real-world positions. This yields nowcasted high-resolution irradiance maps. This step is described in more detail in section 3.1.2.

3.1.1. Modelling of clear-sky index maps and irradiance algorithm

Undistorted sky images are converted to k^* -maps as a basis to compute GHI. Thereby a clear-sky index is assigned to each image pixel using gradient boosting regression from python's scikit-learn library [32]. Gradient boosting was selected as it showed a good balance between robustness, good modelling properties and reasonable computation time in preliminary experiments.

The target values to train our algorithm are clear-sky indices measured at the stations' positions of our network. The model input includes local image features like pixel values in RGB and HSV color space. These are mapped to these positions using the projection method from step (f) (described in further detail in section 3.1.2) for each image within our training dataset (compare section 2.3).

Besides local features our model's input includes global (image) features like image contrast, cloudiness and CBH that account for all measuring stations. Hyperparameters and an extensive list of input features of our irradiance algorithm can be found in the Appendix A. Using these the model is trained to learn the relation between the input and the clear-sky index measured at the respective position.

After training has completed, the model is used to assign clear-sky indices to each image pixel, converting the undistorted image into a k^* -map. To do so, only an ASI image, GHI measurements from the ASI position and information on CBH is required. (The trained model is intended to be applicable to different sites with the same ASI setup and similar meteorological conditions. This is however to be evaluated in a future study.)

3.1.2. Clear-sky index projection

Cloud shadow mapping is a common approach to create areal nowcasts using ASIs and is applied in different variations e.g. in [39,30]. This is usually done using camera projection parameters, CBH and sun position. In this study we extend this concept to not only project cloud shadows but clear-sky index levels directly onto the ground. To do so, we treat all pixels in our clear-sky index images as being located within one two-dimensional plane at CBH. Using the clear-sky index as a continuous variable, no explicit distinction is made between cloudy and cloud-free pixels. Thereby GHI is retrieved in sun exposed and shaded sites in one step. Projected clear-sky indices are subsequently converted to GHI by multiplication with clear sky irradiance yielding a highly resolved GHI map for future situations (Fig. 3 (f)).

Camera projection parameters include a pair of incidence angles (θ and ϕ) that are assigned to each image pixel. These parameters are retrieved in a calibration procedure using images from a checkerboard. The positions of clear-sky indices from each image pixel x_{k^*} and y_{k^*} in a kartesian coordinate system with the ASI position as origin are given as:

$$x_{shadow} = CBH \cdot (\tan(\theta) \sin(\phi) - \tan(\Theta_{sun}) \sin(\Phi_{sun})) \quad (1)$$

$$y_{shadow} = CBH \cdot (\tan(\theta) \cos(\phi) - \tan(\Theta_{sun}) \cos(\Phi_{sun})) \quad (2)$$

Thereby Θ_{sun} and Φ_{sun} denote the sun zenith and azimuth angle. An outline of the geometrical considerations that underly our projection method can be found e.g. in [39].

3.1.3. ASI reference model

Besides the trivial persistence model, we use the model from [8] as benchmark for our novel ASI method. Except for the irradiance retrieval all steps within the reference model are identical to our novel ASI approach.

In [8] irradiance retrieval is a refined version of the method presented in [50]. It is based on assigning binary clear-sky indices to either clear or shaded sites using binary cloud masks. These binary indices are retrieved as the peaks of kernel density estimations on recent measured clear-sky indices. Cloud masks are computed using an adapted version of the cloud detection method from [40]. In the original publication this method was used to create point nowcasts in the position of the ASI. Here we use the clear-sky index projection method from section 3.1.2 to create areal nowcasts.

3.2. Satellite based nowcasts

Our satellite based nowcasting method (SAT-method) is based on [22] and uses data from the geostationary MSG satellite. We use the well-established *Heliosat* method, in a version based on [16] to infer irradiance. This method mainly exploits the broadband visible channel to determine the irradiance transfer through clouds. At that, the pixel intensity is a crucial parameter that serves as a measure for the backscattering and transmission within the clouds. The brighter a pixel appears, the stronger the backscattering ensuing lower irradiance levels on the ground. To detect and forecast cloud movement, we use block matching on two consecutive satellite images.

With this approach forecasts up to several hours ahead can be computed. The spatial resolution of the forecasts is $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ at sub-satellite point and approximately $1.2 \text{ km} \times 2.2 \text{ km}$ in the region of Freiburg. To retrieve irradiance in a certain position (in this study the positions of the measuring stations) satellite pixels are mapped to real-world coordinates, assigning it the pixel closest to the respective position. Given the distances between our measuring stations (Fig. 1) it can thereby occur, that to different stations are assigned to the same pixel. The native temporal resolution is determined by the 15-minute time lapse between two consecutive satellite images. To reach the required 1-minute resolution, timeseries of forecasted clear-sky indices are linearly interpolated (up-sampling). These timeseries are subsequently used for benchmarking and model blending.

3.3. Persistence

Persistence nowcasts assume persistence of prevailing conditions. Taking into account diurnal variations of irradiance, i.e. assuming persistence of clear-sky index, nowcasted GHI_{per} at a given time t is given by [42]:

$$GHI_{per}(t) = GHI_{clear}(t) \cdot k^*(t_0) \quad (3)$$

Thereby $k^*(t_0)$ denotes the clear-sky index at the current moment. In this work we use persistence based on the clear-sky index derived from measurements for each of the stations of the network. This is consistent with the common persistence definition used in most publications. That way persistence nowcasts have the same quality for each measuring station.

In an operational scenario real-time irradiance measurements are not necessarily available at each position of interest. In that case persistence of clear-sky index of the closest irradiance measurement must be applied instead. This reduces the nowcasting accuracy with increasing distance from the measurement. When interpreting our results, it must therefore be considered, that in a real-time scenario persistence nowcasts might be

of lower quality.

3.4. Model blending

In a last step we blend nowcasts of our individual models to a hybrid model with optimized properties. To do so, we use a LT-dependent linear regression. Our hybrid nowcast FC_{hybrid} is the weighted sum of the individual nowcasts. The contribution of each method is LT-dependent:

$$FC_{\text{hybrid}}(LT, x) = FC_{\text{ASI}}(LT, x) \cdot c_{\text{ASI}}(LT) + FC_{\text{SAT}}(LT, x) \cdot c_{\text{SAT}}(LT) + FC_{\text{PST}}(LT, x) \cdot c_{\text{PST}}(LT) \quad (4)$$

FC denotes the respective nowcast (ASI, satellite (SAT) and persistence (PST)) at a certain position x (i.e. the measuring stations' positions within this work) at a certain lead time LT. The corresponding coefficients c depend on the LT, but not on the location. As our measuring network is located within a radius of $r \approx 10 \text{ km}$ and altitude differences of $< 100 \text{ m}$ it is fair to assume similar meteorological conditions for all sites and therefore small dependency of c on the position. We thereby extend our data base for model training and end up with a general hybrid model applicable for all positions within this area, not only the positions of the measuring stations. To derive these coefficients separate regressions are performed on each LT-step, which leads to 16 sets of c -coefficients. In [21] this has proven to be a simple yet effective method to combine results of different PV-forecasting methods. More elaborate non-linear blending approaches have been investigated in a parallel conference publication [45].

3.5. Evaluation concept

We aim for a balanced evaluation framework that yields a comprehensive picture our nowcasting methods. Nowcasting error is analyzed via standard error metrics like RMSE and mean absolute error (MAE). We furthermore examine nowcasting performance under different variability conditions and nowcasting variability itself. Within all evaluations nowcasts are filtered to situations where all methods are available to ensure best possible comparability. We refer to this as availability filtering in the following. Availability filtering is particularly crucial regarding the ASI method, as the field of view of the sky imager sets limitations in space and time which nowcasts can be computed for. Thereby availability depends on station position as well as nowcasting LT.

3.5.1. Error metrics

The error between an observation x_i and the corresponding prediction y_i is given by:

$$\epsilon_i = y_i - x_i \quad (5)$$

To compare model performances, we consider the *root mean squared error* (RMSE) and *mean absolute error* (MAE) and their normalized counterparts ($RMSE_{\text{rel}}$ and MAE_{rel}):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n \epsilon_i^2} \quad (6)$$

$$RMSE_{\text{rel}} = \frac{RMSE}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\% \quad (7)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n |\epsilon_i| \quad (8)$$

$$MAE_{\text{rel}} = \frac{MAE}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\% \quad (9)$$

Thereby \bar{x} denotes the mean of all observations. To investigate systematic over and underestimations the mean bias error (MBE) is used. MBE

is defined as:

$$MBE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=0}^n \epsilon_i \quad (10)$$

$$MBE_{\text{rel}} = \frac{MBE}{\bar{x}} \cdot 100\% \quad (11)$$

In the context of forecasting the skill evaluates the forecast performance compared to a trivial reference method with regard to a certain error metric (e.g. RMSE) [42]. It is calculated from the forecast score S_{fc} in the respective metric, the score of the reference forecast S_{ref} and the score of a perfect forecast S_{perf} (e.g. $S_{perf, RMSE} = 0$):

$$Skill = \frac{S_{ref} - S_{fc}}{S_{ref} - S_{perf}} \quad (12)$$

The skill is positive if the respective score shows an improvement compared to the reference method, zero if its equivalent and negative if it performs worse. It can reach a maximum value of 1 implying a perfect Score ($S_{fc} = S_{perf}$). When computed with a non-trivial method as reference this metric is referred to as improvement score. Here, we evaluate the RMSE skill of our methods in comparison to persistence and the improvement of the hybrid model compared to the single models with respect to RMSE and MAE.

3.5.2. Variability analysis

In this work we analyze nowcasting performances under different meteorological conditions via the clear-sky index and variability of clear-sky index. Thereby we stick to the variability definition proposed by [27]. This definition describes variability as the standard deviation of clear-sky index within a certain time interval:

$$var = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=0}^N i (k_{i+1}^* - k_i^*)^2}{N}} \quad (13)$$

Variability is computed for each nowcasting run along nowcasting LT. This results in a common variability value is assigned to all timesteps within a run. Thereby only nowcasting runs are considered that are available for at least 7 min ahead (compare section 4.1). This way variability is only computed for instances with a sufficient number of datapoints available.

Automatic classifications into different types of meteorological situations or cloud types as used by [20,39] can be challenging to implement and affected by misclassification. Manual selection and classification is time-consuming and not practicable for larger datasets. Variability is a simple and elegant way of bypassing these drawbacks that already provides a lot of valuable insights. Using more sophisticated and detailed approaches, further information can be retrieved.

4. Results and discussion

Prior to examining nowcasting performances we perform an analysis of nowcast availability. Nowcasting performance can vary strongly when evaluated on different datasets. Following this we evaluate our nowcasts as described in section 3.5. Note that the ASI reference method [8] is only used as benchmark for the novel ASI model and is not included in model blending and variability analyses.

4.1. ASI nowcast availability

ASI nowcasts can only be computed within the area to which pixel values are projected to. The extent of this area depends on CBH and sun position. Higher CBHs lead to a larger real-world area of clouds being captured by the ASI. This translates to larger GHI maps on the ground. We define availability as the fraction of available nowcasts $NC_{\text{available}}$

Fig. 4. (a) Fraction of available nowcasts vs. LT for the different stations characterized by station distances from ASI, (b) distribution of measured (instantaneous) k^* before and after availability filtering for all LTs combined (c) variability of measured k^* over LT before and after filtering (all stations combined).

over the number of nowcasts that should have been computed, i.e. the number of base times (BTs). Thereby only instances with corresponding measurements available are considered.

$$availability(LT, station) = \frac{NC_{available}(LT, station)}{BTs}$$

Nowcast availability over LT for each measuring station is shown in Fig. 4(a). An inverse correlation between availability and station distance from the ASI position can be observed: The further a station from the ASI position, the more often it is outside of the projected area. An example of the station in the upper left area being outside the projected area with no nowcast available is illustrated in Fig. 3(f). Besides distance, certain (cardinal) orientations towards the ASI lead to higher availabilities, as the corresponding sun positions occur more often throughout the year. Moreover, our measuring stations are to different degrees affected by gaps and flagged measurements. Therefore, the order of availabilities does not exactly resemble the order of distances.

By extrapolating cloud movements into the future, the projected area is morphed and shifted on the ground. It therefore occurs that the projected area is moved away from certain stations within a nowcast run, causing the run to stop at the respective station at a certain LT. On the other hand, nowcasts are available for certain positions only after a certain LT. Within this evaluation however only nowcast runs are considered, where the respective measuring station is inside the projected area at the beginning of the run. As a result, a decline in availability with increasing LT can be observed. The ASI's limited field of view is one of the major factors limiting the forecasting horizon of ASI nowcasts.

Furthermore, weather conditions have a major impact on forecasting horizons. At an equal real-world cloud velocity, lower CBH translate to higher pixel velocities in the image, which reduces the forecasting

horizon. Higher real-world cloud velocities likewise decrease the forecasting horizon.

Availability filtering changes the composition of our dataset regarding k^* -distribution and k^* -variability (see also section 3.5). Thereby predominantly instances with $k^* \leq 0.5$ (Fig. 4(b)) are removed. The mean variability over all LT of the filtered dataset is higher (≈ 0.06) as for the unfiltered (≈ 0.05) as a high share of stable low CBH situations are filtered out.

Measured k^* -variability over LT before and after availability filtering is shown in Fig. 4(c). The raw dataset shows (almost) constant variability over LT as expected. After availability filtering a decline in variability over LT can be observed as situations with high cloud velocities and broken sky conditions tend to drop out along LT.

An important conclusion must be drawn from the above analysis: By only considering situations where all nowcasting methods are available (which is primarily determined by the availability of ASI nowcasts) not only dataset size, but also composition and properties are modified. The resulting dataset has a larger share of high CBH situations, certain sun positions, high clear sky indices and on average more variable situations.

4.2. Nowcasting error

Nowcasting results of our individual methods and hybrid model evaluated on all measuring stations are shown in Fig. 5. Relative RMSE, MAE and MBE are shown in Fig. 5(a – c). RMSE skill over persistence of our novel and our reference ASI method, as well as SAT and hybrid model is depicted in Fig. 5(d).

Regarding the four individual methods persistence performs best in terms of RMSE for lead times (LTs) up to 2min. For $LT = 0$ the persistence nowcast is the measured value at this exact instance. Starting at

Fig. 5. Nowcasting results of the five different methods on the test dataset (a) relative RMSE, (b) relative MAE, (c) relative MBE and (d) the RMSE Skill with Persistence as reference. Figure (e) shows contributions of each method to the hybrid model over LT and (f) improvement scores of our stepwise hybrid model compared to the respective optimal individual method.

zero, its RMSE quickly rises with LT. Subsequently the ASI takes over until $LT = 11min$ after which the satellite gains a slight edge compared to the ASI (see also RMSE skill, Fig. 5(f)). Our reference ASI method shows the highest RMSE (negative RMSE skill) throughout the entire forecasting horizon. In the original publication positive RMSE skill over persistence was achieved for $LT \geq 1min$ [8]. The study was likewise conducted in Freiburg and covered summer and autumn 2018. Thereby however only point nowcasts for the ASI position were computed. Areal nowcasting induces additional error sources like inaccuracies in CBH and perspective errors causing a decline in nowcasting quality compared to point nowcasts at the ASI position.

Generally forecasting performances of all types of models decrease with increasing LTs. Opposed to that, a decline of RMSE and MAE with increasing LTs can be observed in the satellite curve (Fig. 5(a and b)). As outlined in the previous section, mean variability declines over LT in the

filtered dataset. Remaining lower variability situations at higher LT inherently exhibit lower nowcasting error resulting in the previously mentioned decline of RMSE. The relation between variability and nowcasting error is extensively analyzed in section 4.2.2. Results of the same evaluation but including complete nowcast runs only are shown in Fig. 6. This way the dataset (variability-)composition remains unaltered over LT. Here a steeper increase of RMSE can be observed for the ASI and persistence method, whereas the satellite curve remains on an almost constant level. Moreover, all methods exhibit significantly lower RMSEs throughout all LTs resulting from predominantly lower-variability situations being considered. This also illustrates the dataset dependency of nowcasting performance and the significance of availability filtering our nowcasts to ensure comparability between our models. All in all, the performances of the three methods match the respective temporal scale they are designed for and illustrate the sense of purpose of blending

Fig. 6. Nowcast performance vs. lead time only considering complete nowcast runs (a) relative RMSE and (b) relative MAE. This decreases the number of nowcast runs over all measuring stations from 17,832 to 12,285 (69%).

different methods with varying contributions over LT.

Regarding relative MAE (Fig. 5(b)), our persistence method shows the best individual performance until $LT = 9min$. After that, our ASI method takes over for the rest of the nowcasting interval. The SAT method shows the highest relative MAE for $LT \leq 6min$. After that our reference ASI method shows the highest MAE. RMSE penalizes larger errors and outliers more than MAE. Different error distributions of our models therefore result in different orders and courses of MAE and RMSE curves over LT. An extensive analysis of our methods' error distributions is given in section 4.2.1. Our novel ASI method clearly outperforms the reference ASI method from [8], regarding both RMSE and MAE. Compared to the SAT method it shows lower MAE and RMSE (within a certain LT interval). A further advantage of the ASI over the SAT-method is its higher update frequency.

The relative MBE (Fig. 5(c)) is in the range of -0.5% to 3.5% for all methods, a slight overestimation by our novel ASI method is observed. Our hybrid model exhibits the lowest RMSE compared to any of the individual models over the entire interval. Regarding MAE it performs best for $LT \geq 5min$. The contribution of each method (c-coefficient, compare section 3.4) as a function of LT is depicted in Fig. 5(e). The hybrid method benefits from all three nowcasting methods, exploiting their varying contributions throughout the short-term interval. As expected, these contributions are correlated to the model's performances: The lower the RMSE (Fig. 5(a)) the higher the corresponding models' contribution. For very short $LT (\leq 3min)$ the persistence nowcast makes by far the largest contribution, which quickly decreases throughout the 15-minute time window. The contribution of ASI quickly increases within the first minutes. From $LT \approx 3min$ onwards it is the dominant method within the hybrid nowcast. The contribution of the SAT-method exhibits an almost linear ascend, however remaining behind the ASI throughout the entire 15-minute time interval.

By LT-dependent linear combination of our individual nowcasting results an RMSE improvement score of 5–13% compared to the respective optimal individual method was achieved (Fig. 5(f)). A positive MAE improvement score of up to 6 % can be achieved for $LT \geq 5min$. Our individual methods show different error distributions and therefore different runs of their RMSE and MAE curves (Fig. 5(a and b)). Hence, the RMSE optimization of our hybrid method does not minimize MAE, resulting in a lower MAE than RMSE improvement score.

4.2.1. Distributions of clear-sky index and nowcast errors

To get a better understanding of our models' nowcasting characteristics we examine distributions of nowcasted clear-sky indices and error distributions. Clear-sky index distributions of our nowcasting models as well as corresponding measurements for all LTs combined are shown in Fig. 7. The k^* -distribution of our persistence nowcasts is inherently

Fig. 7. Distribution of clear-sky indices of nowcast and measurement all LT combined.

(almost perfectly) equivalent to the measured distribution.

For the ASI as well as the SAT nowcasts clear-sky indices in the range between $\approx 0.2 - 0.5$ are underrepresented. Values within the intermediate range of around $0.6 - 0.9$ are notably overrepresented.

Measurements exhibit a notable spread around $k^* = 1$. This can be caused by variations in turbidity as well as reflections on cloud bottom sides that cause irradiance levels beyond clear-sky conditions. These aspects are insufficiently reflected within our nowcasting methods and clear-sky model, resulting in a sharp peak at $k^* = 1$. Values beyond that point are underrepresented, whereas this underrepresentation is more significant for the SAT than for the ASI method. Since we use instantaneous values in this study, $k^* > 1$ occur more often as when using averaged values. By design our SAT-method does not predict $k^* > 1.2$. Its initial 15-minute values are linearly interpolated to a 1-minute resolution, such that the majority of instances are interpolated values (compare section 3.2). This creates a smooth nowcast with an over proportional share of values in the intermediate range ($\approx 0.6 - 0.9$) and an underrepresentation for $k^* > 1$ correspondingly. The k^* distribution of our ASI-nowcasts is a result of the RMSE optimized training procedure. To avoid large errors the ASI method favours intermediate values over extreme values. These different nowcasting characteristics also result in distinct error distributions. Relative error counts within selected k^* ranges for two selected LT steps are listed in Table 2.

The persistence method exhibits the sharpest error distribution around zero ($0 - [0.05]$), the lowest count in the intermediate regime ($[$

Table 2

Relative k^* -error counts within given error range of our different methods at LT 2 and 8 Minutes respectively.

Error range	Relative count within k^* -error range				
	LT [min]	Persistence	SAT	ASI	Hybrid
0 – 0.05	2	77 %	34 %	46 %	63 %
	8	60 %	35 %	43 %	49 %
0.05 – 0.25	2	18 %	51 %	45 %	31 %
	8	29 %	50 %	46 %	40 %
0.7 – 1.2	2	1,2%	0,6%	0,5 %	0,4%
	8	2,4%	0,7%	0,8%	0,7%

0.05|–|0.25|) and the highest count within the peripheral high-error region (|0.7|–|1.2|). It includes extreme values and reflects the full range of measurements. The distribution widens up with increasing LT causing the steep increase of RMSE that is shown in Fig. 5.

Our ASI-method shows a more spread error distribution with a lower share around zero and higher counts within the intermediate range. Low error counts can be observed in the high-error region. Our SAT-nowcasts exhibit the same distribution characteristics in a more pronounced way, showing even lower error counts around zero and higher counts in the intermediate range. These distributions are characteristic for relatively smooth nowcasts. ASI and SAT error distributions are nearly constant throughout the entire interval. A major cause for this is the availability filtering as outlined previously.

The error distribution of our hybrid nowcasts combines character-

istics from our three individual methods according to their overall contribution (compare Fig. 5(e)). For $LT = 2mins$ a similar an accumulation of errors around zero can be observed due to the high contribution of persistence nowcasts. For $LT = 8mins$ the distribution widens up and becomes more spread out as the contribution of ASI and SAT nowcasts increase.

4.2.2. Variability analysis

Characterizing cloud conditions by the clear-sky index and variability of clear-sky index is an effective way of analyzing nowcasting performance under different meteorological conditions. By design our individual methods reflect variability on different temporal and spatial scales. Due to its highest spatio-temporal resolution the ASI can produce the most variable nowcasts followed by the SAT method with its coarser resolution. Persistence does not show any variability at all and is therefore not depicted here.

Variability counts of measurements and nowcasts over measured clear-sky index are shown in Fig. 8. Each bin represents a group of samples within a certain clear-sky index and variability range for all LTs cumulated. Bins with a count of less than $n_{min} = 10$ samples were discarded. Instances with very low variability ($var \leq 0.05$) throughout the 15 min interval, represented by the bottom row of bins, resemble the largest share of samples ($\approx 68\%$) as the measured variability distribution reveals (Fig. 8(a)). Situations are hence predominantly stable within the 15 min interval. Clear-sky situations lead to a notable accumulation around $k_{meas}^* = 1$. Stable overcast situations result in another

Fig. 8. Count within different ranges of measured clear-sky index and (a) measured variability, (b) ASI, (c) SAT and (d) Hybrid nowcasted variability for all LTs cumulated. Persistence nowcasts don't show any variability by design and are therefore not displayed.

Fig. 9. RMSE of the clear sky index over measured clear-sky index and variability (a) of ASI, (b) SAT, (c) persistence and (d) hybrid model including all LTs.

accumulation with high counts around $k_{meas}^* = 0.3$. This cluster is more spread out, as radiative properties of clouds can be much more variable than irradiance in clear-sky situations. Count sharply decreases with increasing variability. The maximum variability observed was 0.692, the corresponding bin was filtered out as its count was below n_{min} .

All nowcasting methods (Fig. 8(b and c)) show significantly lower variability than measured (a). Our ASI method shows by far the highest nowcasting variability among our methods. The shape of its variability distribution resembles the measured distribution quite well. Hence our ASI nowcasts are variable in the correct clear-sky index regimes.

Variability of our SAT nowcasts is very limited, however it does reach values > 0 . Its maximum is variability is $var(k_{SAT,max}^*) = 0.027$ and therefore not resolved in the given binning. As this nowcasts is created by linearly interpolating a 15-minute resolution satellite forecast, low SAT-variabilities were expected. Our hybrid method preserves the ASI’s variability to a certain degree yet mitigated due to the contribution of SAT and persistence nowcasts.

Besides variability of our nowcasts themselves we examine the performance of our methods under different variability conditions. RMSE of our nowcasting methods binned by measured variability and clear-sky index is depicted in Fig. 9(a – d). Here we use RMSE instead of relative RMSE, as each bin has a different mean value, and the normalization distorts the overall error distribution. The number of instances within each bin is shown in Fig. 8(a), as mentioned.

Stable situations are inherently easier to nowcast resulting in lower RMSE in this regime for all methods. Our persistence nowcast performs best in stable situations compared to all other methods (Fig. 9(c)). As the lowest variability bins basically resemble situations with a constant clear-sky index (i.e. persistent situations), this result could be expected. With increasing variability, it exhibits the quickest performance drop compared to all other approaches. Due to the high share of stable situations its overall RMSE is still below the ASI and SAT nowcasts for certain LT (Fig. 5(a)).

RMSE remains lower within the k^* -range from approximately 0.7 – 1.1. With increasing variability, the range of lower RMSE tapers.

Larger errors can occur towards k^* extrema, as the difference towards the other extremum is maximized. In variable situations k^* levels can quickly alternate between the extrema, that can lead to maximum errors in nowcasts. Using RMSE as a metric here, which weights outliers stronger, amplifies this effect. In the intermediate k^* regime errors are limited by the k^* -distance towards both extrema.

Within the intermediate k^* range from 0.7 – 1.1 our ASI and SAT method exhibit their best performances. Thereby RMSE increases only slightly towards higher variabilities. Both methods show an over-representation of clear-sky indices in this regime (Fig. 7), which might act beneficial on model performance there.

ASI and SAT nowcasts handle variable situations significantly better than the persistence method. Regarding the SAT method this is mainly due to its smoothing characterizing whereas the ASI can actually reproduce variability to a certain degree (Fig. 8 (b) and (c)).

Our hybrid method shows the lowest RMSE in the low k^* range compared to any of the individual methods. In the intermediate and high k^* range and for variabilities > 0.4 the hybrid model shows higher RMSE which is presumably a result of the contribution of the persistence nowcast.

5. Conclusion

In this work a novel ASI method for high resolution areal nowcasting was benchmarked against a reference ASI model as well as persistence and SAT nowcasts with LTs up to 15min. Linear interpolation was applied to timeseries of SAT nowcasts to match the ASI resolution. Nowcasts from the novel ASI method and SAT and persistence nowcasts were combined via LT-dependent linear regression. The resulting hybrid model shows reduced RMSE compared to the corresponding optimal individual method throughout all LT.

Areal nowcasts were computed every 15min with a temporal resolution of 1min for LTs up to 15min ahead on every fourth day throughout one entire year. The validation was performed with a network of eight measuring stations in the city region of Freiburg, within a radius of $\approx 10km$ around the ASI position.

Table A1

List of irradiance algorithm input features. Local features are mapped to real-world positions via shadow projection. Global features account for all positions within the simulation domain. Elements denotes the number of values that the respective feature holds (e.g. pixel value consists of three color channels).

Name	Description	Elements
Local features		
Pixel value RGB	Pixel value of undistorted ASI image in RGB (Red Green Blue)	3
Red/blue ratio	Red to blue color channel ratio	1
Red/green ratio	Red to green color channel ratio	1
Smoothed pixel RGB	Pixels of smoothed undistorted image. Gaussian filters with different standard deviations for different color channels are applied ($\sigma_{\text{green}} = 50$ pixels; $\sigma_{\text{blue}} = 25, 50$ pixels). Kernel is cropped at 8σ .	3
Pixel value HSV	Pixel value in HSV color space.	3
Mask Pixel	Cloud mask pixel computed using [8]	1
Smoothed Mask Pixel	Pixel of gaussian filtered cloud mask $\sigma_{\text{mask}} = 5, 25, 50$ pixels (compare smoothed pixel RGB)	3
Camera Zenith and Azimuth angle	Camera projection parameters: zenith and azimuth angle of each pixel.	2
Global features		
Fraction clouded	Fraction of pixels cloudy classified in (raw) cloud mask.	1
Fraction shadow	Fraction of cloudy classified pixels in undistorted cloud mask.	1
Sun Angles	Sun zenith and azimuth angle at ASI position for current timestamp.	2
CBH	Cloud base height from ceilometer	1
Contrast	Image contrast as standard deviation of greyscale image. Image is transformed into a greyscale image using Python's OpenCV library [4].	1
Mean values RGB (whole image)	Averages of all pixels of red, green and blue color channels.	3
GHI _{clear}	Calculated clear-sky irradiation at ASI position	1
Mean circumsolar pixel intensity	Average pixel intensity of all color channels in circumsolar region in different angular distances ($0.1^\circ, 0.5^\circ, 1^\circ, 5^\circ, 7^\circ$)	5
Share of saturated pixels in circumsolar region	Ratio of saturated to all pixels in circumsolar region in four different angular distances ($0.1^\circ, 0.5^\circ, 1^\circ, 5^\circ, 7^\circ$). Saturation is the second component in HSV color space. Pixels with $S > \text{Thr}_{\text{sat}} = 0.9$ are denoted saturated.	5
Global features based on real-time irradiance measurements		
$k_{\text{clear/cloud}}^*$	Binary clear-sky indices derived from statistical model from [8].	2
$k_{\text{ASI, meas}}^*$	Clear-sky index measured at ASI position	1
$\overline{k_{\text{ASI, meas}}^*}$	Mean of $k_{\text{ASI, meas}}^*$ over the past 5 min	1
		$\Sigma 41$

Regarding our four individual methods persistence exhibits the lowest RMSE for $LT \leq 2\text{min}$ and lowest MAE for $LT \leq 9\text{min}$. Prevailing meteorological conditions play a major role for the performance of different models. As expected, persistence performs best under stable conditions. With increasing variability, it shows the quickest increase in RMSE in all clear-sky index regimes. By design persistence nowcasts do not reflect any variability at all. The overall relatively good performance of the persistence model results from the high share of stable situations in our dataset (68%) and of the persistence definition applied in this study.

The SAT method shows the lowest RMSE from all individual methods towards the end of the interval ($LT \geq 12\text{min}$) and highest MAE throughout all LT. It produces very smooth nowcasts on a minute timescale due to its linear interpolation, which results in a better performance regarding RMSE than MAE. This smoothing also leads to very limited variability of our SAT nowcasts. Within the clear-sky index range from around 0.7–1.1 our SAT method performs relatively stable with increasing variability. Outside this region RMSE rises with increasing variability. The relatively good performance of our SAT method in high variability situations is a result of smoothing, and not actually reflecting variability.

Within $2\text{min} < LT < 12\text{min}$ our novel ASI method exhibits the lowest RMSE and for $LT \geq 10\text{min}$ the lowest MAE of the individual methods. It clearly outperforms the reference ASI method from [8] at all LT regarding both MAE and RMSE. Error and clear-sky index distribution indicate that our ASI nowcasts exhibit some smoothing but significantly less pronounced as the SAT method. Our ASI nowcasts show the highest variability by far, as this method can reflect short-term irradiance fluctuations. Due to this ability and its smoothing characteristics our ASI methods shows relatively low RMSE in high variability situations. Compared to SAT nowcasts ASI nowcasts have the additional advantage of a higher updating frequency, which wasn't examined in detail in this work.

The spatial coverage of ASI nowcasts is limited and depends on prevailing CBH and sun position. We found an inverse correlation between distance and nowcast availability. Other factors like cardinal orientation towards the ASI play a role for nowcast availability as well. With proceeding LT availability decreases further as clouds move away from the forecasting domain. One way to increase LT and spatial coverage is to work with multiple ASIs with adjacent fields of view, as mentioned (see also section 1). Another approach is to use a hybrid model that fills up gaps in ASI nowcasts with nowcasts from other methods. This way individual methods, designed for different spatio-temporal scales, can be used to complement each other.

Our hybrid model outperforms the three individual methods on any LT by an RMSE improvement score of 5%–13% compared to the respective optimal method. A positive MAE improvement score of up to 6% can be achieved for $LT \geq 5\text{min}$. The ability to nowcast variability is partly passed on from the ASI to the hybrid model, however mitigated due to the contributions of persistence and SAT nowcasts. Variabilities of all nowcasting methods are significantly lower than the measured one. For short LT the hybrid model inherits the ability to reflect the full clear-sky index range including extrema from the persistence method.

More advanced blending approaches beyond linear combination were beyond the scope of this study, but have been presented in a parallel conference publication [45]. Using these, improvement scores of $S_{\text{RMSE}} = 0$ –2% alongside with $S_{\text{MAE}} = 5$ –7.5% over our linear hybrid model could be achieved.

Combination of different nowcasting approaches at image level, e.g. the combination of satellite and ASI images opens up a whole new field of possibilities and first publications [31] promise potential for improvement of irradiance nowcasting. To accurately predict the timing of irradiance fluctuations we see the prediction of cloud movement and development as one of the major challenges. Investigating novel ML-based methods for predicting future cloud situations is the scope of future studies and we see great potential for improvement here. In the

field of short-term precipitation nowcasting novel methods based on convolutional neuronal networks have led to great improvements and outperformed state-of-the-art methods within recent years [2,36].

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A

Features list

Table A1.

Hyperparameters

The irradiance algorithm uses scikit-learn's [32] implementation of gradient boosting regression (sklearn.ensemble.GradientBoostingRegressor()) with default hyperparameters:

`loss='squared_error', learning_rate = 0.1, n_estimators = 100, subsample = 1.0, criterion='friedman_mse', min_samples_split = 2, min_samples_leaf = 1, min_weight_fraction_leaf = 0.0, max_depth = 3, min_impurity_decrease = 0.0, init = None, random_state = None, max_features = None, alpha = 0.9, verbose = 0, max_leaf_nodes = None, warm_start = False, validation_fraction = 0.1, n_iter_no_change = None, tol = 0.0001, ccp_alpha = 0.0.`

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